

Supplementary material - Toulzac *et al.* 2022. Soda maker for field anesthesia as a step towards a non-lethal identification of wild bees and other flower visitors.

Table S1. Data of specimens studied. ITD: Inter-tegular distance. Temp: Air Temperature. Exposure & anesthesia: duration in seconds.

Order	Species	Sex	Flower visited	Locality 1	Locality 2	Date	Voucher number	ITD (mm)	Temp (°C)	Protocol	Exposure (s)	Anesthesia (s)	Survival
Hymenoptera	<i>Andrena sp.</i>	M	<i>Tussilago farfara</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	19/3/21	SP3.21.0041	1.213	21	1	60	110	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Andrena sp.</i>	M	<i>Scilla bifolia</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	9/3/21	SP3.21.0015	1.379	12	1	60	301	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Andrena sp.</i>	M	<i>Arabis procurrans</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	26/3/21	SP3.21.0075	1.429	16	1	60	157	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Andrena sp.</i>	M	<i>Tussilago farfara</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	26/3/21	SP3.21.0074	1.447	16	1	60	102	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Andrena sp.</i>	M	<i>Glechoma hederiae</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	13/4/21	SP3.21.0175	1.731	13	2	60	210	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Andrena sp.</i>	F	<i>Glechoma hederiae</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	26/3/21	SP3.21.0080	1.734	15	1	60	301	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Andrena sp.</i>	F	<i>Mahonia aquifolium</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	2/4/21	SP3.21.0138	2.932	16	2	60	180	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Andrena sp.</i>	M	<i>Scilla bifolia</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	9/3/21	SP3.21.0014	3.142	15	1	60	301	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Andrena bicolor</i>	M	<i>Scilla bifolia</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	12/3/21	SP3.21.0027	2.058	12	1	60	301	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Andrena bicolor</i>	M	<i>Tussilago farfara</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	15/3/21	SP3.21.0039	2.283	16	1	60	175	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Andrena bicolor</i>	F	<i>Chelodinium majus</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	7/4/21	SP3.21.0147	2.394	15	2	60	72	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Andrena sp.</i>	F	<i>Chelodinium majus</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	2/4/21	SP3.21.HP.0028	4.171	24	2	60	61	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Andrena fulva</i>	F	<i>Erica carnea</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	8/4/21	SP3.21.HP.0043	4.402	11	2	60	220	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Andrena haemorrhoa</i>	M	<i>Glechoma hederiae</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	25/3/21	SP3.21.0064	2.711	15	1	60	301	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Andrena sp.</i>	F	<i>Chelodinium majus</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	12/3/21	SP3.21.HP.0007	1.906	14	1	60	170	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Andrena sp.</i>	M	<i>Tussilago farfara</i>	Paris	Jardin des plantes	16/4/21	SP3.21.0190	2.081	17	2	60	93	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Andrena sp.</i>	F	<i>Tussilago farfara</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	26/3/21	SP3.21.0068	2.692	16	1	60	155	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Andrena sp.</i>	F	<i>Tussilago farfara</i>	Paris	Jardin des plantes	16/4/21	SP3.21.0189	2.915	17	2	60	97	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Andrena sp.</i>	M	<i>Tussilago farfara</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	15/4/21	SP3.21.HP.0045	3.091	15	2	60	135	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Andrena sp.</i>	F	<i>Chelodinium majus</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	31/3/21	SP3.21.HP.0020	3.48	24	1	60	35	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Andrena sp.</i>	M	<i>Chelodinium majus</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	25/3/21	SP3.21.HP.0012	2.374	15	1	60	301	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Andrena vaga</i>	F	<i>Chelodinium majus</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	2/4/21	SP3.21.HP.0029	4.256	20	2	60	89	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Andrena sp.</i>	F	<i>Tussilago farfara</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	11/3/21	SP3.21.0018	2.076	13	1	60	220	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Antophora plumipes</i>	M	<i>Lamium purpureum</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	9/3/21	SP3.21.0012	4.942	17	1	60	120	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Antophora plumipes</i>	M	<i>Lamium purpureum</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	7/4/21	SP3.21.HP.0041	5.018	15	1	60	0	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Antophora plumipes</i>	M	<i>Lamium purpureum</i>	Paris	Jardin des plantes	29/3/21	SP3.21.HP.0015	5.194	17	1	60	135	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Antophora plumipes</i>	M	<i>Lamium purpureum</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	7/4/21	SP3.21.0145	5.201	15	2	60	173	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Antophora plumipes</i>	M	<i>Lamium purpureum</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	24/3/21	SP3.21.0051	5.222	24	1	60	106	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Antophora plumipes</i>	M	<i>Lamium purpureum</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	1/4/21	SP3.21.HP.0024	5.269	23	2	60	233	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Antophora plumipes</i>	M	<i>Chelodinium majus</i>	Paris	Jardin des plantes	1/4/21	SP3.21.HP.0026	5.339	24	2	60	202	Yes

Order	Species	Sex	Flower visited	Locality 1	Locality 2	Date	Voucher number	ITD (mm)	Temp (°C)	Protocol	Exposure (s)	Anesthesia (s)	Survival
Hymenoptera	<i>Antophora plumipes</i>	M	<i>Glechoma hederaceae</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	9/4/21	SP3.21.0160	5.366	17	2	60	267	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Antophora plumipes</i>	M	<i>Lamium purpureum</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	7/4/21	SP3.21.HP.0042	5.472	15	2	60	118	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Antophora plumipes</i>	M	<i>Muscaris neglectum</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	12/4/21	SP3.21.0163	5.481	16	2	60	171	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Antophora plumipes</i>	M	<i>Lamium purpureum</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	12/3/21	SP3.21.0020	5.491	12	1	60	301	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Antophora plumipes</i>	M	<i>Rosmarinus officinalis</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	29/3/21	SP3.21.0088	5.492	26	1	60	132	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Antophora plumipes</i>	M	<i>Lamium purpureum</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	1/4/21	SP3.21.0112	5.5	23	2	60	193	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Antophora plumipes</i>	M	<i>Glechoma hederaceae</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	9/4/21	SP3.21.0159	5.573	17	1	60	181	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Antophora plumipes</i>	M	<i>Lamium purpureum</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	13/4/21	SP3.21.0176	5.578	13	2	60	301	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Antophora plumipes</i>	M	<i>Lamium purpureum</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	12/4/21	SP3.21.0165	5.585	17	2	60	195	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Antophora plumipes</i>	F	<i>Rosmarinus officinalis</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	12/4/21	SP3.21.0162	5.594	16	2	60	179	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Antophora plumipes</i>	M	<i>Lamium purpureum</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	12/3/21	SP3.21.0023	5.601	14	1	60	200	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Antophora plumipes</i>	M	<i>Lamium purpureum</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	15/3/21	SP3.21.0040	5.647	17	1	60	110	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Antophora plumipes</i>	M	<i>Glechoma hederaceae</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	29/3/21	SP3.21.0100	5.67	24	1	60	154	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Antophora plumipes</i>	M	<i>Lamium purpureum</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	12/3/21	SP3.21.0021	5.7	12	1	60	301	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Antophora plumipes</i>	M	<i>Glechoma hederaceae</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	31/3/21	SP3.21.0101	5.724	21	1	60	90	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Antophora plumipes</i>	M	<i>Vinca major</i>	Paris	Jardin des plantes	1/4/21	SP3.21.0130	5.725	24	2	60	127	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Antophora plumipes</i>	M	<i>Lamium purpureum</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	7/4/21	SP3.21.0144	5.854	15	1	60	155	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Antophora plumipes</i>	M	<i>Lamium purpureum</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	12/3/21	SP3.21.0022	5.875	15	1	60	240	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Antophora plumipes</i>	M	<i>Glechoma hederaceae</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	9/4/21	SP3.21.0154	5.892	17	1	60	149	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Antophora plumipes</i>	F	<i>Vinca major</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	29/3/21	SP3.21.0096	5.903	25	1	60	142	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Antophora plumipes</i>	F	<i>Rosmarinus officinalis</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	9/4/21	SP3.21.0150	5.964	17	2	60	175	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Antophora plumipes</i>	M	<i>Vinca major</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	29/3/21	SP3.21.0097	5.973	24	1	60	200	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Antophora plumipes</i>	M	<i>Lamium purpureum</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	9/4/21	SP3.21.0153	6.062	17	1	60	232	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Antophora plumipes</i>	M	<i>Lamium purpureum</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	9/4/21	SP3.21.0151	6.066	17	2	60	191	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Antophora plumipes</i>	F	<i>Lamium purpureum</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	1/4/21	SP3.21.0111	6.176	23	2	60	108	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Antophora plumipes</i>	M	<i>Lamium purpureum</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	24/3/21	SP3.21.0059	6.228	18	1	60	260	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Antophora plumipes</i>	F	<i>Lamium purpureum</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	1/4/21	SP3.21.HP.0023	6.609	23	2	60	201	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Antophora plumipes</i>	M	<i>Lamium purpureum</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	7/4/21	SP3.21.HP.0041	5.018	15	2	60	196	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Apis mellifera</i>	F	<i>Erica carnea</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	1/4/21	SP3.21.0115	3.77	24	2	60	200	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Apis mellifera</i>	F	<i>Rosmarinus officinalis</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	12/3/21	SP3.21.0026	3.781	16	1	60	120	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Apis mellifera</i>	F	<i>Mahonia aquifolium</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	31/3/21	SP3.21.0103	3.809	21	1	60	59	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Apis mellifera</i>	F	<i>Erica carnea</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	1/4/21	SP3.21.0114	3.826	24	2	60	68	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Apis mellifera</i>	F	<i>Mahonia aquifolium</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	31/3/21	SP3.21.0104	3.839	21	1	60	61	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Apis mellifera</i>	F	<i>Mahonia aquifolium</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	25/3/21	SP3.21.0066	3.852	15	1	60	301	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Apis mellifera</i>	F	<i>Prunus spinosa</i>	Paris	Jardin des plantes	24/3/21	SP3.21.0044	3.907	18	1	60	255	Yes

Order	Species	Sex	Flower visited	Locality 1	Locality 2	Date	Voucher number	ITD (mm)	Temp (°C)	Protocol	Exposure (s)	Anesthesia (s)	Survival
Hymenoptera	<i>Apis mellifera</i>	F	<i>Muscaris neglectum</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	29/3/21	SP3.21.0092	3.928	26	1	60	63	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Apis mellifera</i>	F	<i>Erica carnea</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	24/3/21	SP3.21.0048	3.943	20	1	60	140	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Apis mellifera</i>	F	<i>Mahonia aquifolium</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	25/3/21	SP3.21.0063	3.943	15	1	60	149	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Apis mellifera</i>	F	<i>Mahonia aquifolium</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	25/3/21	SP3.21.0062	3.951	15	1	60	301	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Apis mellifera</i>	F	<i>Mahonia aquifolium</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	9/3/21	SP3.21.0010	3.958	17	1	60	195	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Apis mellifera</i>	F	<i>Erica carnea</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	24/3/21	SP3.21.0047	3.991	20	1	60	30	No
Hymenoptera	<i>Apis mellifera</i>	F	<i>Glechoma hederiae</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	29/3/21	SP3.21.0098	3.996	24	1	60	50	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Apis mellifera</i>	F	<i>Erica carnea</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	29/3/21	SP3.21.0095	3.997	25	1	60	72	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Apis mellifera</i>	F	<i>Chelodinium majus</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	12/3/21	SP3.21.HP.0008	4.033	13	1	60	301	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Apis mellifera</i>	F	<i>Mahonia aquifolium</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	2/4/21	SP3.21.0140	4.033	16	2	60	184	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Apis mellifera</i>	F	<i>Lamium purpureum</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	26/3/21	SP3.21.0072	4.035	16	1	60	301	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Apis mellifera</i>	F	<i>Erica carnea</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	24/3/21	SP3.21.0049	4.035	20	1	60	301	No
Hymenoptera	<i>Apis mellifera</i>	F	<i>Lamium purpureum</i>	Paris	Jardin des plantes	29/3/21	SP3.21.0086	4.04	20	1	60	56	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Apis mellifera</i>	F	<i>Mahonia aquifolium</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	2/4/21	SP3.21.0134	4.042	20	2	60	67	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Apis mellifera</i>	F	<i>Mahonia aquifolium</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	2/4/21	SP3.21.0135	4.047	20	1	60	68	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Apis mellifera</i>	F	<i>Lamium purpureum</i>	Paris	Jardin des plantes	29/3/21	SP3.21.0083	4.057	16	1	60	35	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Apis mellifera</i>	F	<i>Erica carnea</i>	Paris	Jardin des plantes	29/3/21	SP3.21.0081	4.064	16	1	60	190	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Apis mellifera</i>	F	<i>Mahonia aquifolium</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	9/3/21	SP3.21.0016	4.145	15	1	60	301	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Apis mellifera</i>	F	<i>Erica carnea</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	29/3/21	SP3.21.0094	4.15	25	1	60	59	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Apis mellifera</i>	F	<i>Lamium purpureum</i>	Paris	Jardin des plantes	29/3/21	SP3.21.0085	4.154	20	1	60	180	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Apis mellifera</i>	F	<i>Erica carnea</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	8/3/21	SP3.21.0005	4.158	12	1	60	120	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Apis mellifera</i>	F	<i>Erica carnea</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	26/3/21	SP3.21.0067	4.202	17	1	60	184	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Apis mellifera</i>	F	<i>Erica carnea</i>	Paris	Jardin des plantes	1/4/21	SP3.21.0127	4.23	25	2	60	71	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Apis mellifera</i>	F	<i>Scilla bifolia</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	12/3/21	SP3.21.0028	4.353	12	1	60	301	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Apis mellifera</i>	F	<i>Chelodinium majus</i>	Paris	Jardin des plantes	22/3/21	SP3.21.HP.0009	4.357	11	1	60	301	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Apis mellifera</i>	F	<i>Erica carnea</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	8/3/21	SP3.21.0004	4.384	12	1	60	60	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Apis mellifera</i>	F	<i>Rosmarinus officinalis</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	24/3/21	SP3.21.0054	4.436	18	1	60	20	No
Hymenoptera	<i>Bombus grp. terrestris</i>	F	<i>Mahonia aquifolium</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	13/4/21	SP3.21.0177	5.414	13	2	60	301	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Bombus grp. terrestris</i>	F	<i>Lamium purpureum</i>	Paris	Jardin des plantes	9/4/21	SP3.21.0161	5.432	18	2	60	294	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Bombus grp. terrestris</i>	F	<i>Lamium purpureum</i>	Paris	Jardin des plantes	16/4/21	SP3.21.0188	5.923	17	2	60	293	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Bombus grp. terrestris</i>	F	<i>Lamium purpureum</i>	Paris	Jardin des plantes	22/3/21	SP3.21.HP.0034	6.457	11	1	60	301	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Bombus grp. terrestris</i>	M	<i>Muscaris neglectum</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	24/3/21	SP3.21.0056	6.791	18	1	60	85	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Bombus grp. terrestris</i>	F	<i>Lamium purpureum</i>	Paris	Jardin des plantes	29/3/21	SP3.21.0082	7.23	16	1	60	164	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Bombus grp. terrestris</i>	M	<i>Mahonia aquifolium</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	25/3/21	SP3.21.0065	8.166	15	1	60	301	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Bombus grp. terrestris</i>	F	<i>Mahonia aquifolium</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	26/3/21	SP3.21.0070	8.457	16	1	60	300	Yes

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Hymenoptera	<i>Bombus grp. terrestris</i>	F	<i>Mahonia aquifolium</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	26/3/21	SP3.21.0078	8.926	16	1	60	236	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Bombus grp. terrestris</i>	F	<i>Lamium purpureum</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	31/3/21	SP3.21.0105	9.136	22	1	60	255	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Bombus pascuorum</i>	F	<i>Lamium purpureum</i>	Paris	Jardin des plantes	7/4/21	SP3.21.HP.0040	5.176	14	2	60	250	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Bombus pascuorum</i>	F	<i>Erica carnea</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	1/4/21	SP3.21.0110	5.763	17	2	60	258	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Bombus pascuorum</i>	F	<i>Lamium purpureum</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	9/4/21	SP3.21.0152	5.802	17	2	60	281	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Bombus pascuorum</i>	F	<i>Lamium purpureum</i>	Paris	Jardin des plantes	7/4/21	SP3.21.HP.0036	6.15	12	2	60	301	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Bombus pascuorum</i>	F	<i>Rosmarinus officinalis</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	9/4/21	SP3.21.0158	6.383	17	2	60	301	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Bombus pascuorum</i>	F	<i>Lamium purpureum</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	2/4/21	SP3.21.0142	6.428	20	2	60	233	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Bombus pascuorum</i>	F	<i>Lamium purpureum</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	24/3/21	SP3.21.0053	6.457	22	1	60	233	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Bombus pascuorum</i>	F	<i>Lamium purpureum</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	2/4/21	SP3.21.HP.0035	6.658	20	1	60	286	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Bombus pascuorum</i>	F	<i>Lamium purpureum</i>	Paris	Jardin des plantes	7/4/21	SP3.21.HP.0038	6.719	13	2	60	260	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Bombus pascuorum</i>	F	<i>Lamium purpureum</i>	Paris	Jardin des plantes	7/4/21	SP3.21.HP.0037	6.731	13	1	60	260	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Bombus pascuorum</i>	F	<i>Mahonia aquifolium</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	13/4/21	SP3.21.0178	6.784	13	2	60	301	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Bombus pascuorum</i>	F	<i>Lamium purpureum</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	2/4/21	SP3.21.0141	6.82	20	1	60	272	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Bombus pascuorum</i>	F	<i>Lamium purpureum</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	2/4/21	SP3.21.HP.0032	6.865	20	2	60	235	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Bombus pascuorum</i>	F	<i>Lamium purpureum</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	15/4/21	SP3.21.0181	6.878	15	2	60	180	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Bombus pascuorum</i>	F	<i>Lamium purpureum</i>	Paris	Jardin des plantes	7/4/21	SP3.21.0143	7.072	12	1	60	301	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Bombus pascuorum</i>	F	<i>Lamium purpureum</i>	Paris	Jardin des plantes	7/4/21	SP3.21.HP.0039	7.109	14	1	60	236	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Bombus pascuorum</i>	F	<i>Mahonia aquifolium</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	15/4/21	SP3.21.0185	7.158	13	2	60	301	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Bombus pascuorum</i>	F	<i>Lamium purpureum</i>	Paris	Jardin des plantes	1/4/21	SP3.21.HP.0025	7.49	25	2	60	301	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Bombus pratorum</i>	F	<i>Mahonia aquifolium</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	9/3/21	SP3.21.0007	6.593	16	1	60	120	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Bombus pratorum</i>	F	<i>Mahonia aquifolium</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	8/4/21	SP3.21.0149	6.829	13	2	60	301	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Bombus pratorum</i>	F	<i>Rosmarinus officinalis</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	1/4/21	SP3.21.0117	6.906	26	2	60	301	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Bombus pratorum</i>	F	<i>Lamium purpureum</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	31/3/21	SP3.21.0107	7.057	26	1	60	262	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Bombus pratorum</i>	F	<i>Mahonia aquifolium</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	25/3/21	SP3.21.0061	7.15	15	1	60	196	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Bombus sp.</i>	F	<i>Mahonia aquifolium</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	19/3/21	SP3.21.HP.0033	7.155	21	1	60	301	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Bombus sp.</i>	F	<i>Mahonia aquifolium</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	15/4/21	SP3.21.0183	7.329	15	2	60	228	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Bombus sp.</i>	F	<i>Chelodinium majus</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	11/3/21	SP3.21.HP.0004	8.562	13	1	60	280	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Nomada sp.</i>	M	<i>Chelodinium majus</i>	Paris	Jardin des plantes	29/3/21	SP3.21.HP.0016	1.418	20	1	60	47	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Nomada sp.</i>	F	<i>Tussilago farfara</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	15/4/21	SP3.21.0187	1.817	14	2	60	169	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Nomada sp.</i>	F	<i>Tussilago farfara</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	15/4/21	SP3.21.0186	2.188	17	2	60	75	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Nomada sp.</i>	M	<i>Mahonia aquifolium</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	26/3/21	SP3.21.0079	2.494	16	1	60	195	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Nomada sp.</i>	F	<i>Chelodinium majus</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	31/3/21	SP3.21.HP.0019	2.544	24	1	60	104	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Xylocopa violacea</i>	M	<i>Mahonia aquifolium</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	31/3/21	SP3.21.0109	7.242	28	1	60	301	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Halictus scabiosae</i>	F	<i>Mahonia aquifolium</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	13/4/21	SP3.21.0180	3.616	13	2	60	301	Yes

Order	Species	Sex	Flower visited	Locality 1	Locality 2	Date	Voucher number	ITD (mm)	Temp (°C)	Protocol	Exposure (s)	Anesthesia (s)	Survival
Hymenoptera	<i>Lasioglossum morio</i>	F	<i>Tussilago farfara</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	13/4/21	SP3.21.0174	1.404	13	2	60	98	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Lasioglossum morio</i>	F	<i>Muscaris neglectum</i>	Paris	Jardin des plantes	1/4/21	SP3.21.0122	1.469	25	2	60	52	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Lasioglossum morio</i>	F	<i>Lamium purpureum</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	29/3/21	SP3.21.0093	1.47	25	1	60	0	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Lasioglossum morio</i>	F	<i>Erica carnea</i>	Paris	Jardin des plantes	1/4/21	SP3.21.0120	1.497	25	2	60	52	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Lasioglossum morio</i>	F	<i>Erica carnea</i>	Paris	Jardin des plantes	1/4/21	SP3.21.0128	1.503	25	2	60	54	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Lasioglossum morio</i>	F	<i>Rosmarinus officinalis</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	29/3/21	SP3.21.0090	1.518	26	1	60	32	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Lasioglossum morio</i>	F	<i>Rosmarinus officinalis</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	1/4/21	SP3.21.0119	1.59	27	2	60	63	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Lasioglossum morio</i>	F	<i>Tussilago farfara</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	24/3/21	SP3.21.0060	1.618	18	1	60	160	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Lasioglossum morio</i>	F	<i>Ficaria verna</i>	Paris	Jardin des plantes	12/4/21	SP3.21.0170	1.805	17	2	60	75	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Lasioglossum sp.</i>	F	<i>Scilla bifolia</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	9/3/21	SP3.21.0013	1.773	14	1	60	301	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Lasioglossum sp.</i>	F	<i>Lamium purpureum</i>	Paris	Jardin des plantes	1/4/21	SP3.21.0125	1.778	25	2	60	71	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Lasioglossum sp.</i>	F	<i>Erica carnea</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	26/3/21	SP3.21.0077	1.894	16	1	60	206	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Lasioglossum sp.</i>	F	<i>Mahonia aquifolium</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	26/3/21	SP3.21.0071	1.958	16	1	60	74	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Lasioglossum sp.</i>	F	<i>Chelodinium majus</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	2/4/21	SP3.21.HP.0030	2.254	20	2	60	110	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Lasioglossum sp.</i>	F	<i>Chelodinium majus</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	2/4/21	SP3.21.HP.0031	1.892	20	2	60	54	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Lasioglossum sp.</i>	M	<i>Tussilago farfara</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	26/3/21	SP3.21.0073	1.915	17	1	60	240	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Lasioglossum sp.</i>	M	<i>Tussilago farfara</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	26/3/21	SP3.21.0069	1.934	16	1	60	199	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Lasioglossum sp.</i>	F	<i>Tussilago farfara</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	2/4/21	SP3.21.0131	2.669	25	2	60	128	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Lasioglossum albipes</i>	F	<i>Lamium purpureum</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	31/3/21	SP3.21.0108	2.588	28	1	60	67	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Lasioglossum pallens</i>	F	<i>Lamium purpureum</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	13/4/21	SP3.21.0179	2.23	13	2	60	220	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Lasioglossum sp.</i>	F	<i>Tussilago farfara</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	15/4/21	SP3.21.0184	1.827	13	2	60	296	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Lasioglossum sp.</i>	M	<i>Tussilago farfara</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	26/3/21	SP3.21.HP.0014	2.051	16	1	60	189	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Sphecodes sp.</i>	F	<i>Chelodinium majus</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	31/3/21	SP3.21.HP.0022	3.03	27	1	60	121	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Sphecodes sp.</i>	F	<i>Chelodinium majus</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	2/4/21	SP3.21.HP.0027	3.042	24	2	60	90	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Osmia cornuta</i>	M	<i>Glechoma hederæ</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	9/4/21	SP3.21.0156	3.698	17	2	60	121	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Osmia cornuta</i>	M	<i>Rosmarinus officinalis</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	1/4/21	SP3.21.0118	3.748	26	2	60	56	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Osmia cornuta</i>	M	<i>Muscaris neglectum</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	1/4/21	SP3.21.0116	3.792	26	2	60	57	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Osmia cornuta</i>	F	<i>Chelodinium majus</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	9/4/21	SP3.21.0157	3.956	17	2	60	78	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Osmia cornuta</i>	M	<i>Glechoma hederæ</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	12/4/21	SP3.21.0167	4.031	17	2	60	70	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Osmia cornuta</i>	F	<i>Glechoma hederæ</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	29/3/21	SP3.21.0099	4.19	24	1	60	62	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Osmia cornuta</i>	M	<i>Muscaris neglectum</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	24/3/21	SP3.21.0055	3.571	18	1	60	95	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Osmia cornuta</i>	M	<i>Muscaris neglectum</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	29/3/21	SP3.21.0091	3.845	26	1	60	29	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Osmia cornuta</i>	F	<i>Glechoma hederæ</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	24/3/21	SP3.21.0058	4.451	18	1	60	110	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Osmia cornuta</i>	M	<i>Muscaris neglectum</i>	Paris	Jardin des plantes	9/4/21	SP3.21.HP.0044	3.359	19	2	60	157	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Osmia cornuta</i>	M	<i>Muscaris neglectum</i>	Paris	Jardin des plantes	12/3/21	SP3.21.0029	3.942	14	1	60	215	Yes

Order	Species	Sex	Flower visited	Locality 1	Locality 2	Date	Voucher number	ITD (mm)	Temp (°C)	Protocol	Exposure (s)	Anesthesia (s)	Survival
Hymenoptera	<i>Osmia cornuta</i>	M	<i>Erica carnea</i>	Paris	Jardin des plantes	12/3/21	SP3.21.0031	4.055	13	1	60	301	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Osmia cornuta</i>	M	<i>Muscaris neglectum</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	8/3/21	SP3.21.0002	4.074	12	1	60	233	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Osmia cornuta</i>	M	<i>Erica carnea</i>	Paris	Jardin des plantes	12/3/21	SP3.21.0030	4.463	14	1	60	150	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Osmia cornuta</i>	F	<i>Erica carnea</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	12/3/21	SP3.21.0024	5.016	12	1	60	145	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Osmia cornuta</i>	M	<i>Lamium purpureum</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	12/3/21	SP3.21.0019	5.035	17	1	60	110	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Osmia cornuta</i>	F	<i>Muscaris neglectum</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	12/3/21	SP3.21.0025	5.099	17	1	60	85	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Osmia cornuta</i>	M	<i>Erica carnea</i>	Paris	Jardin des plantes	12/4/21	SP3.21.0168	4.15	17	2	60	134	Yes
Hymenoptera	<i>Abia sp.</i>		<i>Chelodinium majus</i>	Paris	Jardin des plantes	29/3/21	SP3.21.HP.0017	4.197	20	1	60	45	Yes
Hymenoptera	Unidentified Cynipoidea		<i>Chelodinium majus</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	31/3/21	SP3.21.HP.0021	1.11	28	1	60	122	Yes
Diptera	<i>Bombylius major</i>	M	<i>Scilla bifolia</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	9/3/21	SP3.21.0011	4.59	19	1	60	0	Yes
Diptera	<i>Bombylius major</i>	F	<i>Lamium purpureum</i>	Paris	Jardin des plantes	12/4/21	SP3.21.0173	6.106	14	2	60	125	Yes
Diptera	<i>Bombylius major</i>	M	<i>Erica carnea</i>	Paris	Jardin des plantes	12/4/21	SP3.21.0172	6.204	16	2	60	62	Yes
Diptera	<i>Bombylius major</i>	M	<i>Lamium purpureum</i>	Paris	Jardin des plantes	12/4/21	SP3.21.0171	6.238	17	2	60	83	Yes
Diptera	<i>Bombylius major</i>	F	<i>Vinca major</i>	Paris	Jardin des plantes	16/4/21	SP3.21.0191	6.308	17	2	60	68	Yes
Diptera	<i>Bombylius major</i>	M	<i>Ficaria verna</i>	Paris	Jardin des plantes	12/4/21	SP3.21.0169	6.32	17	2	60	57	Yes
Diptera	<i>Lonchoptera sp.</i>		<i>Muscaris neglectum</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	15/3/21	SP3.21.0037	0.952	11	1	60	301	Yes
Diptera	Unidentified Brachycera		<i>Tussilago farfara</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	16/4/21	SP3.21.0192	1.632	16	2	60	96	Yes
Diptera	<i>Anthomyia sp.</i>		<i>Muscaris neglectum</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	7/4/21	SP3.21.0146	2.19	15	2	60	280	Yes
Diptera	Unidentified Brachycera		<i>Rosmarinus officinalis</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	29/3/21	SP3.21.0089	1.303	26	1	60	160	Yes
Diptera	Unidentified Brachycera		<i>Erica carnea</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	12/4/21	SP3.21.0164	2.22	16	2	60	119	Yes
Diptera	Unidentified Brachycera		<i>Mahonia aquifolium</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	19/3/21	SP3.21.0042	3.174	21	1	60	40	Yes
Diptera	<i>Pollenia sp.</i>		<i>Draba verna</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	11/3/21	SP3.21.HP.0005	4.015	16	1	60	10	Yes
Diptera	<i>Sphaerophoria sp.</i>		<i>Tussilago farfara</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	15/4/21	SP3.21.0182	2.4	15	2	60	10	Yes
Diptera	<i>Episyrphus balteatus</i>		<i>Vinca major</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	12/4/21	SP3.21.0166	3.976	17	2	60	89	Yes
Diptera	<i>Eristalis pertinax</i>		<i>Chelodinium majus</i>	Fontainebleau	Station d'Ecologie Forestiere	9/3/21	SP3.21.HP.0002	6.292	19	1	60	30	Yes
Diptera	<i>Meliscaeva auricollis</i>		<i>Tussilago farfara</i>	Paris	Jardin de la Faculte de Pharmacie	15/3/21	SP3.21.HP.0006	3.126	16	1	60	0	Yes